

THE LINGUISTIC AND STYLISTIC SIGNIFICANCE OF FOREGROUNDING IN ANALYZING MASS MEDIA TEXTS

Khudayberganov Ganisher¹, Khudayberganova Marguba²

¹ Senior teacher, Department of Foreign language and literature, University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences, Tashkent, 100149, Uzbekistan

² Senior teacher, English Department, 'Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers' National Research University, Tashkent, 100149, Uzbekistan

¹e-mail: khudayberganovganisher@gmail.com, ²e-mail: safievamarguba@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13219482>

Abstract: In the fast-paced world of mass media, where information bombards us from all angles, the significance of linguistic and stylistic techniques cannot be overstated. Among these techniques, foregrounding stands out as a powerful tool used by media practitioners to captivate audiences, convey messages effectively, and shape public discourse. In this article, we delve into the intricate realm of foregrounding, exploring its linguistic and stylistic significance in analysing mass media texts. This paper intends to inform Mass media materials and its significance and linguistic analysis of foregrounding. Mass media materials are interpreted through text, using different approaches and methods to convey information. The purpose of this scientific work is stylistic and linguistic analysis of the use of foregrounding in mass media tests.

Keywords: Foregrounding, cognitive meaning, discourse analysis, stylistic analysis, linguistic analysis, news, print media, mass media, headlines

2 INTRODUCTION

The use of language in the media, such as specific types of grammatical structure or specific intonation patterns, textual content and its cognitive meaning has given rise to a newly developing field in linguistics. For example, newspaper headlines have unique syntactic features that indicate their grammatical oddity and have long been the subject of analysis by linguists[1]. In a number of studies, the linguistic and stylistic analysis is carried out in ways that illuminate the socio-cultural analysis of the media, which is the reason for the analysis. Basically, the analysis of media texts focuses on changing linguistic features and changing aspects of social context. Although discourse analysis is primarily applied to informal language, recent work has focused on institutionalized forms of discourse, including types of discourse in the media.[2]. For example, many studies have dealt with media interviews[3].

In the formation of the current understanding of media stylistics, it is important to remember two forms of media in particular: the examination of broadcast news on radio and television, and the examination of advertisements, usually in magazines or on television. Some features of the development of approaches to the analysis of each of these speech types will be known. There is also a third media format, the media interview, which covers in-depth news and analysis articles, and conducts extensive research and political research on discussion formats, celebrity and chat show interviews.

News. In the age of mass media, analysis of broadcast news has gained particular attention due to the social importance of the format. From the 1940s to the 1990s, radio and television programs created an atmosphere of influence and controversy around what was said. Also, because of the limited broadcast spectrum that hindered public discourse, the limited number of media channels had certain rules: ownership controls, mandatory program standards, and a complex concept of balance. With the growth of satellite, cable and, more recently, Internet television, 24-hour news and individual news feeds, portable devices such as smartphones have taken over from historically established print media, and broadcast radio as the primary mass source of information and opinion. has overtaken the dominance of broadcast news. In the centralized mainstream period, public broadcasting, radio and television news are still widely used in some settings.

The news formats developed in television news drew on earlier forms of radio news, theatrical promotional films, and earlier forms of print media. But the formats later developed and took shape in new directions. The political impact of television news content and reception, as well as its ever-evolving techniques on the formation of political ideology, are of particular interest in stylistics.

In print media, especially in the early period of stylistics, a particular field of study focused on newspaper discourse, including newspaper headlines.

The wide spread of the newspaper in the 19th century led to an increase in the scope of its analysis, newspaper prose became more like academic prose, and there was an increasingly dense use of passive verbs and relative clauses[4]. These changes focused on a more colloquial style, with changes to greater use of first and second pronouns, contractions, and idioms to broaden the appeal of newspapers and magazines. Through a corpus-based study, the specific role of compressed noun-phrase structures in the linguistic patterns that make up newspaper prose, especially headlines, has been revealed.

Through the analysis, we can see several elements that focus on different types of media discourse and provide an overview of new developments in mass communication studies from the point of view of critical discourse analysis. Media discourse is the most widely heard discourse, which includes news discourse, advertising discourse, television discourse, film discourse, colloquial discourse, visual discourse, etc., and attracts the attention of analysts due to its breadth of fields. Historically, critical discourse analysis emerged and developed in stylistic linguistics, which was developed in the late 1970s, and efforts were made by several European theorists to isolate ideology in speech and to show that ideological processes manifest important elements in the functioning of linguistic features and systems of processes. This, in turn, is closely related to cognitive linguistics. Stylistic linguistics became the critical analysis of speech, and cognitive linguistics became the analysis of speech text. Because information is less word-based—a phenomenon reflected in some commercial discourses—that the semantic relationships expressed by noun-noun sequences are less important, even when students must use pragmatic knowledge to help them or ambiguity in interpretation.

Cognitive analysis of media texts is one of the topical topics of the current period, through which the sphere of influence on the reader and listener is of primary importance. In this case, foregrounding increases the impact of conveying text content. We have observed to what extent the addressee is affected by the use of foregrounding types in modern media texts. And the extent of their use was shown in the percentage of correct use of foregrounding in public media broadcasting and media publication texts.

Indicators of the correct use of foregrounding in...

Figure 1: Use of foregrounding in two types of media text: Print media and Broadcast media

The diagram above shows that despite the popularity of media broadcasts today, the public is less aware of foregrounding in broadcasts than foregrounding in media texts. We can see that print media has always had its influence. It is foregrounding that highlights content in print media texts and prompts people to engage in cognitive analysis.

With the innovations of printing and broadcasting, much of the first stylistic interest focused on transitivity. Transitivity is essentially reflected in the structures of arguments connected with verbs, analyzing the transfer of relations between individuals. When the subject of an active verb becomes an optional agent in the corresponding passive construction, it changes to the object of the active verb. The construction, occupied by different models of transition, offers the public alternative ways of describing social activity in the field of conflict. Provides a basis for a critical approach to news texts.

The heading style can be considered a mere decorative advantage. Rather, depending on the trade-off between information density, copy length, page layout, and readability, it takes on functional aspects. Stylistic analysis is necessary, first focusing on the relevant patterns, to learn what they are, then how they have changed, and then whether function can be determined due to adaptation to production conditions and the perception of expected effects and uses.

Headlines are important in media texts. Because the incentive to listen or read the text is the main element. So what is the importance of Foregrounding in Headlines? Undoubtedly, the most important thing is the correct use of foregrounding, which reveals the content of the media rather than the text itself

Figure 2: An analysis of newspapers known for their correct use of foregrounding in their headlines and their public impact

"

Total orders for periodical press publications (newspapers and magazines) amounted to 613,045 copies. 392,450 of them corresponded to newspapers. The 5 most requested newspapers from him (251,168) accounted for about 64% of the total ordered newspapers"[6], and these newspapers: "Xalq so'zi". "Hurriyat", "O'zbekiston ovozi" and "Ishonch" It is not difficult to understand that the impact wave in the cognitive analysis of the articles published in these newspapers is in the masterful use of the headlines. Among them, to what extent can the headlines used in these articles attract public attention? It was demonstrated through a statistical approach with linguistic and stylistic analysis. It was a matter of foregrounding and to what extent it was correctly applied by publishers. From our analysis, it can be seen

that 2 of the given newspapers ("Xalq so'zi", "Ishonch") were able to attract public attention with their headlines, and we can see that foregrounding is used wisely and correctly in their headlines. And vice versa, in the other 2 ("Hurriyat", "O'zbekiston ovozi"), this indicator is much lower.

To sum up, Mass media have always been used as a mirror of society's development, as the main tool for shaping people's consciousness, outlook, and political level. Like all industries, the media has experienced a period of significant development. For this, all the conditions have been created in our country, and the activity of foreign mass media, the types of texts used in them, and the ability to perform a stylistic analysis of the text are of great importance

REFERENCES

- [1] MARDH, Ingrid (1980): *Headlines: On the Grammar of English Front Page Headlines*. Lund: CWK Gleerup.
- [2] HERITAGE, John (1985): "Analyzing news interviews: aspects of the production of talk for an overhearing audience", in Teun Adrianus Van Dijk (ed.): *Discourse and Dialogue (Handbook of Discourse Analysis, vol. 3)*. London: Academic, pp. 95-119.
- [3] HUTCHBY, Ian (1991): "The organization of talk on talk radio", in Paddy Scannell (ed.): *Broadcast talk*.
- [4] Jones, B. D., & Wolfe, M. (2010). Public policy and the mass media. *Public policy and mass media: The interplay of mass communication and political decision making*, 17-43. London: Sage, pp. 119-137.
- [5] https://xs.uz/uz/post/gazeta
- [6] Douthwaite J. *Towards a Linguistic Theory of Foregrounding* Torino, 2000.
- [7] Heritage, John (1985): "Analyzing news interviews: aspects of the production of talk for an overhearing audience", in Teun Adrianus Van Dijk (ed.): *Discourse and Dialogue (Handbook of Discourse Analysis, vol. 3)*. London: Academic, pp. 95-119.
- [8] https://xs.uz/uz/post/gazeta
- [9] Hutchby, Ian (1991): "The organization of talk on talk radio", in Paddy Scannell (ed.): *Broadcast talk*.
- [10] Jones, B. D., & Wolfe, M. (2010). Public policy and the mass media. *Public policy and mass media: The interplay of mass communication and political decision making*, 17-43\London: Sage, pp. 119-137.
- [11] Mardh, Ingrid (1980): *Headlines: On the Grammar of English Front Page Headlines*. Lund: CWK Gleerup.